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Changthangi Sheep:

The pride of Ladakh

Abstract

Changthangi breed is generally described as *Changthangi* sheep as per the name of its breeding tract. Local farmers of the area called it by Chagluk meaning sheep of northern plateau (Chang = Northern, Thang = Plateau / Plain, Luk = Sheep). The breed is reared for quadruple purpose: mutton, wool, manure and dung energy. This breed of sheep sustains the economy of *Changpas* to a greater extent but next only to pashmina goats. Changthang region has harsh climatic dryness with very low rainfall where temperature varies from -40°C to $+40^{\circ}\text{C}$. Almost every household is having 50-100 sheep. The color of the sheep varies from complete black to white and brown. Most of the animals have a mixture of these three colors however the white is predominant. The average wool production is found to be 1.5 to 2 kg and is higher in male than female. Both horned and polled pattern animals are found in *Changthangi* breed and very few are polycerous also. The adult weight of Changthangi sheep ranges from 40-52 kgs in males and 35-42 kgs in females. These are seasonal breeders and breeding season is from July-November while main Lambing season is December to March. The occurrences of the diseases are very less but very few common diseases affecting the *Changthangi* sheep are Diarrhea, Clostridial diseases, Brucellosis, Foot and Mouth disease, Ecthyma and Sheep pox.

Key Words: Changthangi sheep, Chagluk, Changpas, Ladakh

Introduction

For many Changpas, rearing of animals, and consuming and selling their produce (milk and its products, hair and meat) is the only means of livelihood. Changthangi sheep is a multipurpose breed and is utilized for wool, guard hair, pelt, meat, milk production and, dung energy. The breed is having two fleece coats; the outer course and the inner coat, which protects the breed during harsh winters when temperature drops to -40 degrees Celsius. The wool is naturally grown on the sheep to protect it from the cold. At the beginning of summer season, in May and June, the local people comb the wool with the help of a local comb specially designed for this purpose or do shearing. The average wool production is found to be 1.5 to 2 kg and is higher in male than female, out of

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which almost 700-800 grams of ne wool is produced. Almost every household is having 50-100 sheep. The wool is used for weaving of the woollen products. Each family is having sufficient raw wool and they do not need to procure it from any other source. The Changpas also use the pelts as clothing as well as flooring material in their tents, which keeps their tents warm in the freezing temperature. They use the dung of this sheep as a source of fuel energy for cooking of foods and keeping their tent warm. They use milk of this sheep for making of salt tea. Buddhists usually do not slaughter or kill their animal but they do eat their meat whenever animal dies naturally or is killed by some predator.

Distribution and breeding tract

Distribution of native tract in terms of longitude and latitude extends between 32°-3 to 34°-0 North and 77°-5 to 79°-10 East. The geographical area of the breeding tract is about 24,000 squares km. The breeding tract of the Changthangi sheep comprises of various villages located in main and collateral valleys of Changthang area. It includes valleys of Rong, Nyoma, Kuyul (all these three valleys are basin of the river Sindh), and with some collateral valleys, Puga and Rupsu, Kharnakand Tso Kar of Nyoma block of Changthang. The villages of Cheshule, Pangong and Krygam valleys are the remaining portion of the breeding tract and these areas falls in Durbuk block of Changthang. These valleys are mostly of about 30 kms in length and of varying breadth. The breeding tract lies in Leh district. This area falls in cold arid region of western subcontinent between the Korakaram and the Greater Himalayas interwoven with barren and rugged mountains forming some big and small side valleys. On the North-East side of the breeding tract

is the Tibet and China and its southern side is bounded by Chamba and Lahul-Spiti Districts of Himachal Pradesh. The terrain is mostly mountainous and denuded. The Changthang area is divided into two rural developmental blocks- Durbuk and Nyoma. The Changthang is derived from a Tibetan word meaning northern plains (Chang =northern, thang = plains). Whole of the breeding tract was divided into 12 and villages. The elevation of the breeding tract varies from 3,340 to 4,560 m above MSL and these elevations correspond to Liksy and Korzook villages, respectively. The physiography of the area is mountainous with long valleys between them. The animals are reared extensively in the pastures up to 5,200m above MSL.

Physical traits of Changthangi sheep

Colour: The colour ranges from complete black to white and brown. Most of the animals has a mixture of these three colours however the white is predominant.

Horns: Both horned and polled animals are present and very few are polycerous also.

Ears: Both the ears are pendulous.

Wattles: Wattles were observed only in 2% and majority of the animals did not have any wattle.

Head: Atypical convex head with a long tapering face.

Tail: The tail is medium or short. The tail is thin and straight in all the cases.

Udder pattern: The females have medium sized udder with small conical teats.

Legs: Legs are short giving a low-set conformation

Morphometric traits

Body weight(kgs):Adult Male: 40-52, Adult Female:35-42

Body Length (cms): Adult Male:50.02–70.00, Adult Female: 45.00–67.00

Chest Girth (cms): Adult Male: 70-85, Adult Female: 67-78

Height at withers (cms): Adult Male:47-60, Adult Female: 45-55

Ear Length (cms): Adult Male:5.0-7.5, Adult Female: 5.0-7.0

Tail Length (cms): Adult Male:7-8.5, Adult Female: 6.5-8

Reproduction traits

Age at first mating (months): Male 24-30, Female 26-32

Age at first estrus (months): 16-18

Estrus cycle duration (days): 21-22

Estrus duration (hours): 36-48

Age at first lambing (months): 28-30

Lambing interval (months): 12-14

Litter size: 1

Lifetime number of lambs: 6-8

Production traits

Wool traits

Clean wool yield (%): Male: 71.50, Female: 70.00

Fiber diameter (μ): Male: 32.17, Female: 30.18

Staple length (cms): Male 13.90, Female: 12.95

Number of crimps per centimeter: Male: 4.8, Female: 3.98

Medullation %age: Male: 12.85, Female: 10.07

Carcass traits

Age at slaughter (months): Male: 22-32, Female: 30-62

Weight at slaughter (kgs): Male: 25, Female: 24

Carcass weight (kgs): Male: 17.78, Female: 16.50

Dressing percentage: Male: 46, Female: 45

Milk traits: No milk is taken from the sheep; however, the sheep has sufficient milk for their lambs.

Diseases and their management: The occurrences of the diseases in its native tract are very less. Common bacterial diseases affecting the are Diarrhea and Clostridial diseases and occasional incidence of Brucellosis are also reported. The commonly reported viral diseases are Foot and Mouth disease, Ecthyma, Sheep pox. The sheep are sometimes vaccinated against Foot and Mouth disease, Pox and Clostridial disease (Lamb dysentery, Struck, Malignant oedema, Pulpy Kidney, Black's disease). For protection against the Clostridia disease multi-component Clostridial vaccine is administered.

Male

Female

Flock of Changthangi sheep